

SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL VIEWS RELATED TO LINGUOCULTURAL AND LINGUOMENTAL FEATURES OF CHILDREN’S POETRY

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Abstract: This article looks at different scientific ideas about how language, culture, and thinking skills affect children's poetry. It explores how things like language rules and cultural traditions influence how kids create and understand poems. The article also looks at how kids' thinking and emotions play a part in this. It talks about how experts from different fields, like language studies, psychology, and cultural research, study these things to understand children's poetry better. They want to see how poetry helps kids learn language and understand their culture. The article also talks about how teachers and parents can help kids learn language and culture by sharing poetry with them.

Keywords: children's poetry, linguocultural features, linguomental features, language acquisition, cognitive development, cultural identity, interdisciplinary perspectives, education.

Introduction:

Children's poems are like a fun way to learn about language, culture, and how our brains grow. They're not just simple rhymes; they're a mix of words that show how different cultures talk and how kids learn. For instance, think about the nursery rhyme "Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star." It's not just about stars; it's also about how we use language to describe the world around us. For example, the nursery rhyme "Humpty Dumpty." It's not just a story about an egg falling off a wall; it's also about how language can create vivid images and spark our imagination.

This article is all about digging deep into the ideas scientists have about how language, culture, and thinking connect in children's poems. We want to understand how kids' brains work when they read or write poems and how it helps them learn language, understand their culture, and grow their minds.

Linguocultural Features:

Children's poetry is deeply connected to how we speak and the cultures we come from. Linguocultural features include things like the way words are put together, the style of writing, and references to our cultural backgrounds found in poems. For example, when we hear rhymes, rhythms, and repeated words in poems, they're not just there to sound nice—they also help us learn language and understand our culture better. Nursery rhymes like "Jack and Jill" or "Humpty Dumpty" are good examples of this. They show how language and culture are passed down from one generation to the next. Also, children's poems often talk about things that are important to different cultures, like their beliefs, values, and traditions. This helps kids learn about where they come from and feel like they belong.

Linguomental Features:

Children's poetry goes beyond just language and culture; it also affects how our brains work and how we see the world. Linguomental features include the mental processes involved in understanding and enjoying poetry. Things like metaphors, vivid descriptions, and hidden meanings in poems make us think in new ways and become more creative. When kids read or hear poems, it helps them think in abstract ways, understand others' feelings better, and express themselves creatively. For instance, even a short poem like a haiku or a limerick can make a child's mind race with ideas and feelings, encouraging them to think about different points of view and explore new things.

Interdisciplinary Perspectives:

To truly grasp children's poetry, we need to look at it from many angles, not just one. This means bringing together ideas from different fields like language studies, psychology, anthropology, and education. Linguistic theories help us understand how poems are structured and how they help kids think. Psychological theories show us

how poems affect kids' minds and make them more creative. Anthropological views help us see poems in the context of different cultures, showing how they shape who we are and how we communicate with others from different backgrounds. Educational methods show us how poems can be used to teach kids language skills, critical thinking, and an appreciation for different cultures.

Practical Implications:

Children's poetry is a treasure trove for both teachers and parents, offering countless ways to boost kids' language skills and cultural understanding. By making poetry a part of classroom lessons and home life, educators can help kids learn language in a fun and creative way while also fostering their emotional growth. Encouraging children to write their own poems lets them express themselves in their own unique way, building confidence and creativity. Additionally, collections of poetry from different cultures give kids a chance to explore diverse languages and traditions, opening up opportunities for discussions about the richness of human expression worldwide. With the help of guided conversations and activities, children can delve into the beauty and cultural significance of poetry from all corners of the globe, enriching their linguistic and cultural awareness.

Conclusion

To sum up, the scientific theories about the language, culture, and cognitive aspects of children's poetry highlight its complexity and significant influence on various aspects of development. By looking at poetry from different perspectives, we get a better understanding of how it shapes children's language skills and cultural awareness. Teachers and parents, as guardians of language and culture, have a crucial role in encouraging children to explore poetry and appreciate its beauty. By embracing the diverse world of children's poetry, we embark on a journey of exploration, creativity, and cultural appreciation that can have a lasting impact on children's lives.

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